

IMPACT OF LEADERSHIP AND PERSONALITY ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT - MALAYSIAN SMEs STUDY

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Abstract - Leadership and personality are few of the factors which explain the leader-subordinate relationship in any organisation. Studies seldom explored the relationship between leadership and personality on commitment of organisational members differentiating gender role in the small and medium scale industries. Hence this study focuses on the relationship between leadership and personality on commitment of SME managers. Following cross sectional descriptive study design with purposive sampling, the study conducted among 285 managers of SMEs in the Klang Valley region of Malaysia. The study used SPSS to analyse the data providing managerial implications to SME entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Leadership, personality, gender, SME

I. INTRODUCTION

SMEs are the major industrial units which contribute national economy. The effectiveness and efficiency of the SMEs depends on human factor which contribute to productivity. This claim leads us to argue that human commitment to work will be an interesting factor to be examined into to justify the past claims. There are several factors that influence the commitment of employees within an organisation such as leadership style, behaviours,, personality, motivation, job satisfaction, and decision-making [1] This has led researchers to emphasise the importance of reviewing the factors that influence individual's organisational commitment which affects the productivity of an organisation. This research was done on Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Malaysia, focuses on two factors - leadership style and personality as the main determinants to organisational commitment [2], [3]

II. LITERATURE AND HYPOTHESIS

A. Leadership and organisational commitment

Davenport [25] highlighted the leadership styles have a pivotal predictor to organisational commitment. Lot of studies in the literature explain indicates the relationship of the leadership styles; transformational and transactional leadership on the organisational commitment [4],[5],[6]. Prime constraint for any firm is to incite a feeling of commitment among the employees and implanting commitment. Major apprehension of this research is to

examine whether leadership theory and organisational commitment are applicable in the small and medium scale industries located in Malaysia. This research endeavours to answer the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: Leadership style of managers will have significant influence on organisational commitment

B. Personality and organisational commitment

It is stated that [7], [8] personality have positive influence to organisation commitment because the individuals who are sociable, conscientious and with steady feelings are eager to be more dedicated to their firm. Few studies have been carried out to investigate the relationship between organisational commitment and five factor model of personality [9], [10] lights upon significant positive association between these factors. From the above argument the following hypothesis has come up.

Hypothesis 2: Personality of managers will have significant influence on organisational commitment

C. Gender and organisational commitment

Existing literatures have suggested that gender is one of the key factors to impact on the organisational commitment [11],[12] have mentioned that employed men showed a small but significant higher organisational commitment compared to employed women. However, there has been research to show that gender has no effect on the commitment of an organisation [13]. From the above argument the below hypothesis has come up;

Hypothesis 3: There will be significant relationship of gender toward organisational commitment.

D. Gender, Leadership Style and Organisational Commitment

According to [14] female leaders in organisation settings incline to be more democratic and participative than men leaders, whereby men leaders have incline a tendency to learn more towards autocratic behaviour. Furthermore, several researches stated that [15] male leaders stressed more to the transactional leadership style, while female leaders tend towards a transformational leadership style. Fewer studies were conducted to analyse the moderating role of gender in its relation between leadership style and organisational commitment in

SMEs. Hence this study poses the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 4: Gender moderates the influence of leadership of managers and organisational commitment

E. Gender, Personality Style and Organisational Commitment

Studies pointed out strong relationship between employee commitment to their job and it can be measures with respect to the trait of personality that have in each person [16] According to [17] gender have a positive significant influence the personality, because the differences behaviour man and female in term of decision making, helping, concerning, dealing and commitment.

Hypothesis 5: Gender moderates the influence of personality of managers and organisational commitment

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Sampling

The sample for this research focused on working managers in SMEs have the duty of carrying out trade and services. The middle level of managerial staffs is confirmed for the study since there is high attrition of such staffs in SMEs. The researcher collected 285 questionnaires back from 300 set of questionnaire distributed, and followed purposive sampling. The study location is the Klang Valley region of Malaysia.

TABLE 1 MEASUREMENT

No	Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
1.	Leadership Style	27	0.889
2.	Personality	44	0.873
3.	Organisational Commitment	24	0.863

According to the pilot study that has conducted, it shows the Cronbach's Alpha for the leadership style is 0.889. While the Cronbach's Alpha for personality is 0.893 and the Cronbach's Alpha for organisational commitment is 0.836. Overall the results show that the Cronbach's Alpha exceeding 0.8. Hence, it can be assumed that internal consistency for this questionnaire is considered to be good.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

TABLE 2 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENT

Demographic	Categories	Total	Percentage
Gender	Male	188	66.
	Female	97	34
Age	20-30 years	56	19.6
	31-35 years	116	40.7
	36-45 years	49	17.2
	46-55 years	64	22.5
Marital Status	Married	194	68.1
	Single	83	29.1
	Widower	2	1.4
	Divorced	4	1.4
Level of Education	High School	50	17.5
	Diploma	55	19.3
	Bachelor		58.9
	degree	168	3.6

	Master degree	10	0.7
	Doctor degree	2	
Experience	10-16 years	193	67.7
	17 – above	92	32.3
Turnover	0	181	63.5
	1	22	7.7
	2	43	15.1
	3	28	9.8
	4	2	0.7
	5	5	1.8
	9	2	0.7
	10	2	0.7

The table 2 provides the detail of the demographics of respondents based on gender. The result shown that out of the 285 respondents in the survey, 188 or 66% are male and the rest of respondents are females which is 97 respondents or 34%. Further the respondents in this study represented four range of age. Firstly, the range of 20-30 years old have 56 respondents (19.6%). Secondly, the range of 31-35 years old respondents have 116 respondents (40.7%). Thirdly, the range of 36-45 years old respondents have 49 respondents (17.2%). Lastly, the range of 46-55 years old which is 64 respondent (22.5%). The profile of respondent in table points out that 285 respondents have took part in this survey, 194 or 68.1% respondents who are married, and 83 respondents or 29.1% are single. Further, the widower only 4 or 1.4% respondents, lastly, only 4 or 1.4% respondents are divorced. The details level of education of managers has indicated that only 50 respondents (17.5%) were from high school level, followed by 55 respondents (19.3%) were from diploma level. The 168 respondents (58.9%) were from the bachelor degree level, and the master level only have 10 respondents (3.5%) as well as the doctor level only have 2 respondents (0.7%). The experience of managers, whereby the experience categories become two such 10-16 years and 17-above of experience. In addition, the employee who already has experience working in 10-16 years indicated 193 or 67.7% respondents. Followed by 17- years and above was work experience with number of 32.3% respondents. Research hypotheses in this study are tested using multiple regression analysis with the objective of measuring the relationship between dependent and independent variables.

Hypothesis 1: Leadership style of managers will have significant influence on organisational commitment

TABLE 3 MODEL SUMMARY LEADERSHIP STYLE ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SE
1	.648 ^a	.412	.410	.48580

a. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership

Based on the table 3, the R square value is 0.412 (R²= 0.412) which means 41.2% of the organisational commitment intention can be explained by leadership, while the rest is influenced by other factors that are not conducted in this research. Furthermore, R is 0.648

indicates there is significant positive relationship between the independent variable, leadership and the dependent variable, organisational commitment.

TABLE 4 ANOVA LEADERSHIP STYLE ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Means Square	F	Sig.
Regression	6.975	1	6.975	29.556	.000 ^b
Residual	66.789	283	.236		
Total	73.764	284			

a. Dependent variable: Organisational Commitment
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership

Table 4 shows about ANOVA whereby the result F Value is 29.556 with the significant is 0.000 level. The result shows that there is a significant relationship between leadership style and organisational commitment with the prediction equation, (F=29.556, $p < 0.05$).

TABLE 5 COEFFICIENTS OF LEADERSHIP STYLE ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	SE			
Constant					.000
Leadership	2.456	.221	.388	11.154	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational Commitment

Table 5 indicated the coefficients level stated that the number in beta is 0.388 for leadership, which is a strong, positive, significant correlation ($\beta = 0.388$, $p < 0.05$) between leadership style and organisational commitment. Thus the result is positively significant between leadership style and organisational commitment. In conclusion, it has proven the first hypothesis (H1) which stated leadership style of managers will have influence on organisational commitment

Hypothesis 2: Personality of managers will have significant influence on organisational commitment.

TABLE 6 MODEL SUMMARY PERSONALITY ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SE
1	.701 ^a	.491	.490	.46882

a. Predictors: (Constant), Personality

Based on the table 6 indicated that the R square value as 0.491 ($R^2 = 0.491$). Which means that 49.1% of organisational commitment is predicted by personality, while the rest is influenced by other factors that are not conducted in this research. Furthermore, R is 0.701 indicates there is significant positive relationship between variable that indicated as a strong correlation.

TABLE 7 ANOVA PERSONALITIES ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Means Square	F	Sig.
Regression	11.562	1	11.563	52.608	.000 ^b
Residual	62.201	283	.220		
Total	73.764	284			

a. Dependent variable: Organisational Commitment
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Personality

Table 7 shows that the F Value is 52.608 with the significant as 0.000 levels. Continued by the df (degree of freedom) whereby df represent the number of independent variable is 1 which is personality. The result indicated that there is significant relationship between personality and organisational commitment with the prediction equation, (F=52.608, $p < 0.05$)

TABLE 8 COEFFICIENTS OF PERSONALITY ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	SE			
Constant				7.309	.000
Personality	1.849	.25068	.396	7.250	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational Commitment

Table 8 indicated the coefficients levels with the number in beta is 0.396 for personality, which is a strong, positive, significant co-relations ($\beta = 0.396$, $p < 0.05$) between personality and organisational commitment. Thus the result is positive significant between personality and organisational commitment. In conclusion, it has proven the second hypothesis (H2), personality of managers will have influence organisational commitment.

Hypothesis 5: There will be significant relationship between gender and organisational commitment

TABLE 9 MODEL SUMMARY GENDER ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SE
1	.687 ^a	.471	.470	.32176

a. Predictors: (Constant), Gender

Based on the table 9, the R square value is 0.471 ($R^2 = 0.471$), hence, it has shown that 47.1% of the organisation commitment intention is predicted by the gender. Furthermore, as seen from the summary model table, R is 0.687 indicates there is a strong positive relationship between the two variables.

TABLE 10 ANOVA GENDER ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Means Square	F	Sig.
Regression	.991	1	.992	30.460	.003 ^b
Residual	58.621	283	.178		
Total	59.612	284			

a. Dependent variable: Organisational Commitment
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Gender

Table 10 shows that the F Value is 30.460 with the significance is 0.003 level. Continued by the df (degree of freedom) whereby df represent the number of independent variable is 1 which is gender. The results have indicated that there is significant

relationship between gender and organisation commitment with the prediction equation, ($F=30.460$, $p < 0.05$).

TABLE 11 COEFFICIENTS OF GENDER ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	SE	Beta		
Constant					
Gender	1.78	.262		7.24	.000
	.398	.052	.338	7.17	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational Commitment

Table 11 indicated the coefficients level which have beta number 0.338 for personality, which there is a strong, positive, significant co-relations ($\beta= 0.338$, $p < 0.05$) between gender and organisational commitment. Thus, the results have proven on the fifth hypotheses (H5), there is a significant relationship between gender and organisational commitment.

Hypothesis 3: Gender will moderate the effect of leadership style and organisation commitment.

TABLE 12 MODEL SUMMARY GENDER MODERATE LEADERSHIP STYLE AND ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.601 ^a	.361	.360	.49833
2	.700 ^a	.490	.489	.48017

a. Predictors: (Constant), Gender
 b. Predictor: (Constant), Gender, Leadership

Based on the table 12, the model 1, R square value is 0.361 ($R^2= 0.361$) which means 36.1% of organisational commitment intention is predicted by gender. While the model 2, R Square is 0.490 ($R^2= 0.490$) which means 49.0% of organisational commitment intention is predicted by leadership with gender as moderator. Furthermore, when seen the summary model table, in the model 1 which R is 0.601 ($R=0.601$) continued the model 2 which R is 0.700 ($R=0.700$). It means there is relationship between two variables and also it has indicated a positive correlation relation.

TABLE 13 ANOVA GENDER MODERATE LEADERSHIP STYLE AND ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Means Square	F	Sig.
Regression	3.485	1	3.485	14.035	.000 ^p
Residual	70.278	283	.248		
Total	73.764	284			
Regression	8.745	2	4.372	18.964	.000 ^f
Residual	65.019	282	.231		
Total	73.764	284			

a. Dependent variable: Organisational Commitment
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Gender
 c. Predictors: (Constant), Gender, Leadership

Table 13 shows about the ANOVA result. The model 1 have F Value for gender is 14.035 and the significant is 0.000 level. Continued by the df (degree

of freedom) whereby df represent the number of independent variable is 1 which is gender. While model 2 have the F value for the gender, and leadership towards the organisational commitment are 18.964 and the significance is 0.000 level. Followed by the number of independent variable is 2 which is gender and leadership. The result indicated that gender moderate the influence of leadership style on organisational commitment with prediction equation, ($F = 14.035$, $p < 0.05$) & ($F = 18.964$, $p < 0.05$).

TABLE 14 COEFFICIENTS OF GENDER MODERATE LEADERSHIP STYLE AND ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	SE	Beta		
Constant	3.95	.089			.000
Gender	.233	.062		.217	.000
Constant	2.86	.254		11.083	.000
Gender	.170	.061	.159	2.770	.006
Leadership	.274	.057	.273	4.776	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational Commitment

Table 14 portray the coefficients level. The result show that gender have significant influence on organisational commitment, where the significant level is 0.001 ($\beta= .233$, $p < 0.05$). In the sixth hypothesis: gender moderate the effect of leadership style and organisational commitment. The result shows a significant relation because gender ($\beta= 0.159$, $p < 0.05$) and the leadership ($\beta= 0.273$, $p < 0.05$) is found significant as well. In conclusion, the table 4.21 has proven the sixth hypothesis (H6), gender will moderate the effect of leadership style and organisational commitment.

Hypothesis 7: Gender will moderate the effect of personality and organisation commitment.

TABLE 15 MODEL SUMMARY GENDER MODERATE PERSONALITY AND ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SE
1	.619 ^a	.383	.380	.4983
2	.721 ^a	.519	.510	.4616

a. Predictors: (Constant), Gender
 c. Predictor: (Constant), Gender, Personality

Based on the table 15 indicated that the model 1 R square value is 0.383 ($R^2= 0.383$) which means 38.3% of organisational commitment intention is predicted by gender. While the model 2 R Square is 0.519 ($R^2= 0.519$) which means 51.9% of organisational commitment intention is predicted by personality with gender as moderator. Furthermore, when seen the summary model table, in the model 1 which R is 0.619 ($R=0.619$) continued the model 2 which R is 0.721 ($R=0.721$). It means there is relationship between two variables and also indicated the correlation.

TABLE 16 ANOVA GENDER MODERATE PERSONALITY AND ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Means Square	F	Sig.
Regression	3.485	1	3.485	14.035	.000 ^b
Residual	70.278	283	.248		
Total	73.764	284			
Regression	13.676	2	6.838	32.093	.000 ^c
Residual	60.088	282	.213		
Total	73.764	284			

a. Dependent variable: Organisational Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Gender

c. Predictors: (Constant), Gender, Personality

Table 16 shows about the ANOVA result. The model 1 have F Value for gender is 14.035 and the significant is 0.000 level. Continued by the df (degree of freedom) whereby df represent the number of independent variable is 1 which is gender. Thus, the result for model 1 is a significant relationship. While model 2 have the F value for the gender, personality toward organisational commitment is 32.093 and the significant at 0.000 level. Continued by the model 2 df represent the number of independent variable is 2 which is gender and personality. Thus, the result for model 2 is having significant relationship. The result indicated that gender moderate the influence personality on organisational commitment with prediction equation, ($F = 14.035, p < 0.05$) & ($F = 32.093, p < 0.05$).

TABLE 17 COEFFICIENTS OF GENDER MODERATING PERSONALITY ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	SE	Beta		
Constant	3.95	.089		44.70	.000
Gender	.233	.062	.217	3.746	.000
Constant					
Gender	2.189	.269		8.14	.000
Personality	.183	.059	.171	3.150	.002
y	.464	.067	.375	6.916	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational Commitment

Table 17 portray the coefficients level. The result is gender have significant influence to the organisational commitment, because the gender indicated the level significant is 0.000 ($\beta = .217, p < 0.05$). In the seventh hypothesis: gender moderate the effect of personality and organisational commitment, the result shows a significant relation because gender ($\beta = 0.171, p < 0.05$) and the personality ($\beta = 0.375, p < 0.05$) is found significant as well. In conclusion, the table 4.22 is proving the seventh hypothesis (H7), gender will moderate the effect of personality and organisation commitment.

V. DISCUSSION

The first research objective is to determine whether leadership style of managers significantly influence organisational commitment.

It is reasonable to hypothesise that behaviour of the leaders prone to have its effect on subordinates. Past studies pointed out the association between leader's behaviour and organisational commitment. Especially the transformational leadership is usually related with

anticipated outcomes of an organisation [18]. The second research objective is to determine whether personality of managers has significant influence on organisational commitment. The result indicated that personality of managers have influence on organisational commitment. By understanding the manager personality, harmonious relations between employee and manager can be built which further entrust the organisational commitment of the employee, whereas this harmonious relation could make the employee stay longer within the organisation. This findings is supported by [3], [19] who emphasis that there is a positive significant relationship between personality and organisational commitment.

The third research objective in this study is to determine whether gender has any significant influence on the organisational commitment. The result has shown that there is a significant relationship between gender and organisational commitment. Previous researches have clearly indicated that women have a tougher time balancing family and work; these will indirectly lead to a lower organisational commitment among female managers compared to male managers [20]. Organisational commitment will be influenced by gender due to different non-job-related obligations, among male and female. From the result, it can be concluded that male and female managers have impacted on the organisational commitment.

The fourth research objective in this study is to determine whether gender moderates the influence of leadership style of manager and organisational commitment. The result shows that gender significantly moderate influence of leadership style on organisational commitment. It means gender stereotype have relationship between leadership style and organisational commitment. The female leaders have shown high levels of attitudinal commitment than male leaders [21]. The present findings also supported by [22], [23] indicated male leaders are more to the transactional leadership style, while female leaders tend towards transformational leadership style.

The fifth research objective in this study is to determine whether gender moderates the influence of personality of managers and organisational commitment. The result shows that gender moderate the relationship between personality and organisational commitment. The male leaders focus to solve the problem and keep track the mistake until somehow the problem arises, and then they will solve it [24]. The personality of women tends to make the comfortable relation between the manager and the employee. The sensitiveness and open-hearted make the leader also could feel what the employee feels so the manager can know what they should do, rather than men who rarely concerns to their subordinates. The above discussion indicates that both personality

and leadership are major factors linked to organisational commitment in SMEs.

VI. IMPLICATION

A. Managerial

The objective of this research was to determine the antecedents of organisational commitment in SMEs. The study clearly shows the effect of leadership impact on employee commitment. This indicates that managers leadership style have better inference on the subordinate's behaviour. It is expected that the leaders in the organisation needs to have transformational leadership that ensure better affective commitment among the employees. A supportive and transformational leadership have better lead towards employee commitment.

The variations in the gender related leadership indicates that female managers have more transformational leadership in comparison with males. Male members have the transactional leadership. Justified use of transformational and transactional leadership may provide better acceptance and accountability from the subordinates. The confusion should be when to use transitional and when to use transformational. The managers need to obtain better training and development related to these two forms of leadership and its situational use in order to get better accountability of senior manager's leadership among the subordinates, in SMEs.

Further the study findings also indicate that top management should consider personality of the managers as one of the factor which can bring better organisational commitment among the members in SMEs. Though each of the big five personality traits represent a continuum between two extremes, in the real world, majority managers personality profile lies somewhere in between the two polar. It is very important pay attention to the personality profile of the managers as far as their involvement with the subordinates are concerned, which is paving way towards better commitment at work. Commitment towards work, innovation behaviour, ability to work in teams, emotional intelligence and performance etc. are the outcome of leader 'personality. This study provides ideal information about leadership style and personality towards organisational commitment.

The leaders need to change the leadership style who tends to be autocratic leadership needs to change and become more transformational leadership. Because transformational leadership tends more respect, good relationship with subordinate, sensitive with the concern of subordinate, creative and good communication with a clear vision. The top management needs to think to employ more female managers rather than male managers, because as the research knows there is less female leaders in SMEs. Female leaders tend to be transformational leadership rather than male leaders, whereas the transformational is the most predictor to influence individual become commitment. It is well established that the society

have a differential perception towards male and female difference in leadership style. It is necessary to look in different ways the leadership impact and the styles, in modern organisations. An organisation should engage in a portfolio of HR initiatives that are mutually reinforcing, as opposed to being contradictory. The male managers need to have transformational leadership style to advance an organisational commitment. More training and development to the male managers on transformational leadership style which is highly envisaged here.

VII. CONCLUSION

Human aspects of SMEs are seldom studied by research scholars especially in the Malaysian industrial context, where majority industrial establishments are coming under SMEs. This research aims to determine the influence of leadership and personality on organisational commitment. This quantitative research provides better insight and predictability into the effect of leadership and personality on the commitment of employees. It is also indicated that the HR managers and the top management of the SMEs should work on reducing gender differentiation by understanding the differential leadership styles. This study extends better contribution to managerial implications as well as theoretical implications explaining the impact of both leadership and personality on organisational commitment in SMEs.

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